

Democracy & Changing Politics

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Abstract:

In India, parliamentary democracy holds a very important place. Countries like Great Britain, Switzerland, and Australia have also adopted parliamentary democracy. In a parliamentary democracy, the country is governed through representatives elected directly by the people through voting. It would not be wrong to say that in a parliamentary democracy, the people themselves are indirectly the rulers. The types of democracy, the importance of the people in a democracy, the ruling politicians, the changing role of leaders playing the role of the opposition party, the changing party loyalty of leaders for selfish reasons, the frustration of the voting public, the increasing apathy and carelessness among the public towards voting, the neglect of constituencies by elected leaders, the failure of central and state government schemes to reach the poor, the use of old practices under new names, the lack of strong leadership in the opposition party, and the changes in leaders due to self-interest and their adverse effects on the public are all impacting Indian politics.

While India is striving to be recognized as a developed nation, the frequent changes in power in the constituent states appear to be a growing problem. The increasing regionalism, linguistic divisions, and shifting loyalties in democratic politics are leading to underdevelopment instead of national development.

Keywords: Indian democracy, politics, authoritarianism, party loyalty.

Introduction:

69 percent of the Indian population lives in rural areas. In ancient times, problems arising in villages were solved within the village itself. Although there was no formal education system in ancient villages, security, cleanliness, and self-defence were maintained. Protecting themselves and their villages from foreign invasions was the function of the village defence force created in those villages. This is reflected in

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historical records mentioning the soldiers employed by the former landlords, chieftains, and feudal lords. Rural villages have been meeting their needs within the village itself since ancient times. In ancient times, Panchayats existed in India. Until the Mughal period, villages were self-sufficient, and their administration was carried out through Panchayats. The Balutedar system (a system of hereditary village servants) was prevalent in every village. The specific system of rural local self-governance that has been established is called Panchayat Raj. Maintaining cleanliness in the village/hamlet/settlement is the primary duty of the villagers, but this is often neglected today. Due to this reason, both the central and state governments are seen implementing cleanliness campaigns in rural areas along with urban areas, which means that leaders are paying attention to government schemes.

After independence, India adopted parliamentary democracy. In a parliamentary democracy, representatives elected directly by the people through voting govern the country. In a parliamentary democracy, the people are considered sovereign. The value of the people's vote is extremely important in a democracy. India is considered the world's largest democratic country. The framers of the constitution chose parliamentary democracy over presidential democracy to prevent the establishment of dictatorial, communist, or capitalist governments in the country. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, the chairman of the Constitution Drafting Committee, studied the constitutions of countries like France, Canada, America, Great Britain, Australia, Russia, China, and Japan, and completed the large written constitution with 395 articles, 12 chapters, and 22 schedules in two years, eleven months, and eighteen days. The seeds of democratic governance can be seen in the ancient Greek city-state of Athens. It would not be wrong to say that democracy existed in India in ancient times.

India has a multi-party system. There are national parties like the Congress, Bharatiya Janata Party, Samajwadi Party, and Bahujan Samaj Party, as well as regional parties like Akali Dal, National Conference, Asom Gana Parishad, Shiv Sena, Telugu Desam, and Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam. To gain power, parties give promises to the people, prepare their party's development plan, present it to the public, and get their candidates elected through the ballot box to form their government. The leader of the party that secures a majority in the Lok Sabha or the state legislature becomes the Prime Minister or Chief Minister. The party that does not get a majority plays the role of the opposition. Since 2014, the Bharatiya Janata Party government, under the leadership of Hon. Narendra Modi, has been in power at the centre. The BJP claims that India has been developing since then. However, the role of the opposition party appears to be constantly changing. In this research paper, the researcher has attempted to present parliamentary democracy, public

awareness regarding representatives, the changing loyalties of representatives, with a special reference to the politics of Maharashtra state, and the changing role of the opposition party in politics.

Democracy:

Democracy is the Marathi equivalent of the English term 'democracy', derived from 'Demos' meaning common people and 'Cracy' meaning power. In modern times, the term democracy is seen to be used in the sense of indirect democracy.

A government run by the people for the people is a democratic state. Democracy means a state governed by representatives elected by the people through open, impartial elections based on the votes of the adult population.

Indian politics operates within the framework of the country's constitution. India is a parliamentary, secular, democratic republic. The President of India is the head of state and the first citizen of India, while the Prime Minister is the head of government. The Prime Minister is the head of government, but this term is not found in the constitution. Based on a federal structure, there is a single constitution for the central government and the states. In India, the constitution has established the unquestionable supremacy of Parliament. The government is run by representatives elected by the people. The Rajya Sabha (Council of States) represents the states of the Indian federation, while the Lok Sabha is considered the house of the people. There is a provision for a bicameral legislature. The constitution has provided for an independent judiciary, headed by the Supreme Court. The court's functions include protecting the constitution, resolving disputes between the central and state governments, inter-state disputes, striking down central and state laws that violate the constitution, protecting citizens' rights, and issuing writs. In cases of violation, it works to enforce them. The President holds the highest position. The President is recognized as an integral part of Parliament. A bill becomes law only after his signature. The President has the authority to send the bill back to the Parliament for reconsideration.

Parliamentary Democracy:

According to the characteristics of the parliamentary system of government, India will have two heads. One, the head of the state, the constitutional head, who will be the nominal head, whose position will be like that of the King or Queen of England. Two, the real head, the head of the government, whose position will be like that of the Prime Minister and the Cabinet. The nominal head will be the President, and the real power will be in the hands of the Cabinet, including the Prime Minister. The President will exercise

executive power according to the advice of the Prime Minister and the Cabinet. The Central Executive consists of the President and the Cabinet, including the Prime Minister.

Before the 42nd Constitutional Amendment (before February 1, 1977), there was a debate regarding whether the advice of the Cabinet was binding on the President or not. One school of thought was that the Cabinet's advice was binding on the President, and the President was merely a constitutional, formal, and nominal head. There was no explicit mention in the Constitution, in any form, that the President must accept the advice of the Cabinet. Therefore, some constitutional experts were of the opinion that the President of India was not merely a nominal or ceremonial head of state. The 42nd Constitutional Amendment is important because it ended the uncertainty regarding the advice of the Cabinet. The 44th Constitutional Amendment in 1978 brought about a change in the role of the Prime Minister and the Cabinet. Now, the President can send the Cabinet's advice back to the Cabinet for reconsideration, but if the Cabinet sends the advice back to the President, with or without changes, the President has to accept it and act accordingly.

Indian Parliament:

According to Article 79 of the Indian Constitution, the Parliament consists of the President, the Rajya Sabha, and the Lok Sabha. The President is an integral part of the Indian Parliament. The Rajya Sabha is the upper house, and the Lok Sabha is the lower house. The structure of these two houses, the nature of their powers, and their place in the Indian political system are completely different. It is also expected that they represent the diversity of society and represent different groups and organizations. The Rajya Sabha, the upper house, represents the states. The Rajya Sabha of India has 250 members. The Vice-President of India is the Chairman of the Rajya Sabha. One member is elected as the Deputy Chairman. The house performs functions such as introducing bills, discussing them, and approving them. The Lok Sabha is the lower house of Parliament. It consists of representatives directly elected by the people. The Lok Sabha of India has 545 members. One member is elected as the Speaker and another as the Deputy Speaker. The leader of the party that secures a majority is chosen for the post of Prime Minister. He is administered the oath of office and secrecy by the President. A cabinet is formed to assist him. The Prime Minister, with the advice of the cabinet, acts as the real head of the government. The Prime Minister and the cabinet remain in office as long as they maintain a majority in the Lok Sabha.

On similar lines, in the federal system, each state has a legislature called the Legislative Assembly. Some states have a bicameral legislature, consisting of a Legislative Assembly and a Legislative Council. The nominal head of the state is the Governor, while the real head is the Chief Minister. The leader of the party

that secures a majority in the Legislative Assembly takes the oath of office and secrecy as the Chief Minister, and a cabinet is formed to assist him.

Party System:

Political parties have become an integral part of the political system. The existence of at least one or more political parties is observed in all countries. Although thinkers like Rousseau, George Washington, and Jayaprakash Narayan have highlighted many flaws of political parties, their importance in the political system has not diminished. Even though Indian thinkers like Manabendra Nath Roy and Jayaprakash Narayan strongly advocated for a party-less democracy, the possibility of this dream becoming a reality seems unlikely. In modern times, political parties hold an important place in all political systems. This reality has to be accepted by everyone. Political parties organize the demands and expectations of the people and also represent them. In a democratic system, political parties have a crucial role. In a parliamentary system of government, both the ruling party and the opposition party hold important positions. During elections and at other times as well, various political parties present their ideologies to the public. The party whose ideology and program resonate most with the people gains a majority. The majority party comes to power and manages the affairs of the state, while the opposition party works to keep a check on the government.

A political party is a political organization with a common ideology, program, objectives, and goals. It is described as a group of people constantly striving for the objective of gaining power. Political parties perform many functions such as participating in elections, bringing about peaceful changes in power, establishing relations between the people and the government institutions, and building political leadership. Because political parties perform many functions necessary for an organized and orderly political life, they have become an integral part of the modern political system.

Indian society is divided into numerous small and large groups based on various factors such as language, religion, region, and culture. Various political parties have come into existence to ensure participation in different groups or to influence political policies and decisions. Until 1977, the Congress party was the only party in power; in the subsequent period, other parties came together to form coalition governments. Currently, in India, since 2014, the central government is led by the Bharatiya Janata Party under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi.

The Role of Contemporary Opposition:

The victorious march of the Bharatiya Janata Party, which began with the Lok Sabha elections under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi, appears to be the beginning of a changing ideology in Indian politics. This ideology includes many regional parties and politics based on regional identities. The BJP has formed governments in various states with the help of regional parties. After the 2019 assembly elections, the Shiv Sena, a regional party, found itself in a difficult situation. The Shiv Sena, which fought for Marathi identity, joined hands with the Nationalist Congress Party and the All-India Congress Party to form a government under the leadership of Uddhav Thackeray. At this time, the Shiv Sena party seems to have abandoned its main ideology of Marathi identity. This hurt the sentiments of many Marathi people. It also doesn't seem that the government was formed on the issue of development versus identity. In Maharashtra, and not only in India but all over the world, various identities are being nurtured, shaped, and reshaped. Taking the example of the Shiv Sena in Maharashtra, the party's journey has been shaped by various kinds of antagonistic politics. Initially opposing Gujarati traders, the Shiv Sena later turned against South Indians. During the renaming of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University to Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, the same Shiv Sena is seen taking an anti-Dalit stance. In later periods, it appears to be anti-Muslim. For three to four years, the Shiv Sena, which had been at odds with the BJP, abandoned its Marathi identity and formed a government in Maharashtra by joining hands with the Congress and Nationalist Congress Party (NCP). Eknath Shinde, who was a minister in that government, has once again invoked Marathi pride and formed a government with the BJP to develop Maharashtra under the leadership of Narendra Modi. Presenting himself as the true champion of the Shiv Sena's cause and rushing to the aid of the people, Eknath Shinde has now become the Chief Minister. The very leaders who claimed that Marathi pride was being compromised and development work was stalled under the previous government, and that then-Finance Minister Ajit Pawar was not releasing funds, broke away from the Uddhav Thackeray government and formed a government with the BJP. These same leaders then had to include Ajit Pawar as Deputy Chief Minister in their government, and coincidentally, the finance portfolio has once again been given to Ajit Pawar. The question inevitably arises: where has the loyalty of these leaders gone, who were previously criticizing Ajit Pawar when he was in the opposition? Given the threats and exposure of scams against opposition leaders by the central BJP government through agencies like the ED and CBI, it would not be wrong to say that these opposition leaders have sold their loyalty to the voters.

These incidents are being observed not only in Maharashtra but also in other states. Jyotiraditya Scindia, who was loyal to the Congress party, has also joined the BJP.

In contemporary politics, everyone aspires to come to power, and when power is given to them, they don't know how to empower the people. As a result, power is lost, and this cycle continues.

The current situation is extremely delicate because many regional parties have high expectations from their allies. If these expectations are not met, they withdraw support or create trouble. Some are playing politics using Hindu, Dalit, and Muslim communities as vote banks. The public is so foolish that they respect the religious aspects of these politicians but don't think about how their own progress will be achieved. What is good for our country? Some feel that since we are South Indians, why should we contribute to politics controlled by North Indians? This is the situation.

In 1999, Sharad Pawar left the Congress party for his own selfish reasons and formed the new Nationalist Congress Party. Loyalty to the party seems to be changing.

The low participation of women in politics is also becoming a source of changing politics. Concerns remain regarding reserved seats for women in elected positions. The issue of training and preparing women for leadership roles is also a matter of concern. In Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra, it has been observed that women lack education and training to understand the procedures in the Panchayats. The family plays a crucial role in women's participation in government. Family connections can help women in elected positions at the national and local government levels. Concerns have been raised about the role of women, but women are seen to have a significant influence on policy decisions. For men, the most important issues are roads, irrigation, education, and water, while welfare issues such as violence against women, childcare, and maternal health are also likely to be considered.

Lack of competent leadership:

There is a noticeable lack of knowledgeable leaders in the state government or the central government. It is observed that leaders are given portfolios in which they have no expertise. Leaders are seen using their positions to settle political scores and rivalries. Instances of leaders switching allegiances have increased. Party changes are seen happening for personal gain. It would not be wrong to say that the current politics is focused on self-enrichment. Casteism is raising its head in politics. Religion is being used to garner votes. Political leaders who are abandoning party loyalty are emerging. While young people have competitive exams for jobs, politicians are seen promoting one family member after another. The political atmosphere appears to be deteriorating.

Conclusion:

Although India's population and population density have increased, the level of understanding among political leaders is not as expected. Today, leaders who are closely associated with one party are found forming alliances with other parties for their own selfish interests tomorrow, which raises questions about party loyalty. Corruption is raising its head because leaders are not certain how long they will remain in power. There are divisions within parties. Women's participation in politics is not as significant as it should be.

In contemporary politics, with power in the hands of BJP-led leaders, leaders from other parties are seen changing their parties due to fear of ED, CBI, and other investigations. Voters are being misled. The votes cast by voters for one party sometimes result in that party being in power and sometimes in the opposition. In Maharashtra, in the 2019 assembly elections, Shiv Sena + BJP and Congress + Nationalist Congress Party fought together, but in government formation, Shiv Sena + Congress + Nationalist Congress Party formed the government by keeping the BJP out. This shows that politicians are breaking the promises made to the public. It is becoming difficult to say which party is in the opposition because it is sometimes in power and sometimes in the opposition. This means that regional parties are becoming puppets in the hands of the central government. This is endangering democracy. The anti-defection law is weak. Power politics revolves around the pursuit of power. Politicians are seen breaking the promises made to the public.

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